

DELAMINATION INITIATION PREDICTION FROM CONSTITUENT BEHAVIOR

J.R. Gregory^{1,2}, S.M. Spearing²

*Department of Mechanical Engineering¹
and*

*Technology Laboratory for Advanced Composites²
Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, MA 02139*

ABSTRACT

There is currently no method available to determine the delamination toughness of a composite from its constituents' properties. This is an important link that could help accelerate the insertion of materials via an analytical process that connects material behavior at various lengthscales. A finite element model is created to investigate the contribution of inelastic deformation at the crack tip in a composite double cantilever beam specimen to the composite toughness. The constituent properties are explicitly incorporated into the analysis through the use of a global-local model. The global J -integral is representative of an experimentally determined fracture toughness while the local J -integral accounts for inelastic deformation at the crack tip. Fracture measurements are carried out on IM7/977-3 and its neat resin in order to obtain data for incorporation into and comparison with the model. In addition, the experiments allow for determination of the important fracture mechanisms. The model is interrogated by varying the plastic behavior of the resin and the constraint on the resin. Using the neat resin fracture toughness as a local fracture criterion is found to be inadequate, but data on constrained resin behavior may be used. The tool is useful for evaluating candidate resin and fiber systems if the resin inelastic behavior is known and an estimate of the constrained resin toughness can be made. Data from adhesive bond tests using neat resins with thin layers on the order of the interply resin thickness could be used as an estimate of composite toughness while the model could be used to explain the differences between the neat resin and composite toughnesses.

KEY TERMS: Composites, delamination, toughness prediction, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

The Accelerated Insertion of Materials-Composites (AIM-C) effort has been created to establish a methodology that will reduce the cost and time required to insert composite materials into aerospace products [1]. Modeling is used to simulate material response and failure, thereby reducing the number of tests required to characterize a material for design certification and verification. Model predictions may be used to eliminate tests in which material properties are well defined by the models, and dictate tests that are essential to the simulations.

Modeling of composite behavior within AIM-C takes advantage of the various length-scales found in composites. Evaluation of a candidate composite material begins at the constituent level with the choice of matrix and fiber. One may then examine the effects of the constituent properties on the lamina, laminate, and structural behavior. Ply level hygrothermal and elastic properties can be determined from constituent properties using a range of micromechanics models [2, 3]. However, an important area that is lacking predictive capabilities is in the determination of composite fracture behavior, particularly delamination initiation, from constituent properties. Delaminations are some of the most common manufacturing defects found in composite aerospace parts and hence modeling techniques that utilize fracture based on an existing flaw are often an appropriate modeling tool for predicting failure or analyzing the effects of defects. Determining composite behavior from constituent behavior is a fundamental component of accelerating the insertion of materials because it allows for an initial

evaluation of candidate resins and fibers without actually undergoing the costly process of creating a composite system.

The research described herein is a part of the larger AIM-C effort and is an attempt to develop a predictive tool that can determine the delamination initiation toughness of a composite material based on the constituent properties. Such a tool would also potentially have applications in durability and adhesive bond analyses where resin and/or adhesive behavior play critical roles. Delamination properties of a composite system are investigated experimentally along with general mechanical properties of its constituents. A finite element model (FEM) is created to analyze the behavior of the composite at the global and local (constituent) level. The results of the numerical analysis must then be coupled with an appropriate fracture criterion.

BACKGROUND

Epoxies have been used in composite materials because of their relatively high stiffness and stable behavior in hot/wet conditions. However, their Achilles' heel has been their poor fracture toughness, which often manifests itself in delamination or off-axis ply cracking. Many experimental studies have been conducted examining the role of the resin on the composite fracture process. Figure 1 shows a collection of Mode I (opening) interlaminar toughnesses for several composites versus their associated resin toughnesses [4]. It is interesting to note that composites that contain brittle resins have fracture energies higher than those of their neat resins while composites with tougher resins are more fracture resistant but do not benefit from the increase in neat resin toughness to nearly the same extent.

independent of test specimen configuration, was the initiation toughness [7]; crack propagation toughness was highly dependent on specimen geometry. Furthermore, it was shown that initiation toughness is independent of ply orientation in a laminate [8] and that fiber bridging is an artifact of the test method [9].

Several hypotheses were proposed based on the experimental evidence to explain the change in composite toughness with increasing resin toughness. Explanations for the higher composite toughness than the associated constituent brittle resin included the increased surface area of the composite fracture surface (analogous to a “corrugated roof”) over a neat resin fracture surface, the impinging of cracks on misaligned fibers, and the stress state ahead of the crack tip decaying

more slowly than that in the neat resin, causing stresses to be more evenly distributed [5]. Other analyses of the constrained resin stress state have indicated that in composites the fibers can create stress concentrations for resin and increase the extent of matrix yielding and therefore the fracture toughness [10], while in adhesive joints a decrease in thickness causes the local tensile stresses ahead of the crack

Many studies were performed to determine which mechanisms played a key role in the interlaminar fracture process. Several fracture mechanisms were discovered through delamination examinations including fiber bridging, fiber debonding, fiber pullout, cohesive resin fracture, microcracking ahead of crack tip, and resin crack tip plastic deformation [5, 6]. However, it is clear that plastic deformation and/or damage at the crack tip of the matrix is the dominant mechanism in interlaminar fracture, assuming adequate fiber/matrix interfacial strength, because these processes require the most energy. It was also discovered that the only measured property that was a true material property, that is,

Figure 1. Collection of composite interlaminar fracture toughnesses versus neat resin toughnesses [4].

tip to act over a much longer distance than in the bulk material, creating a much longer plastic zone [11]. Although there is little consensus as to what mechanism is primarily responsible for composites with brittle resins, there is general agreement on the explanation for the decreased toughness of a composite with a ductile resin when compared to the neat resin toughness. The theory is that the fibers reduce the amount of resin volume available to deform or microcrack and thus absorb energy that would otherwise be applied to resin damage in the relatively large plastic zone created in a ductile resin [5]. Thus, even though the composite toughness is greater than that of composites with brittle resins, the potential of the tougher matrix is not fully realized.

In other related experimental work, Chai attempted to correlate the toughness of resins in adhesive bonds to composite interlaminar fracture toughness [7]. The work has shown that the composite toughness coincides with the adhesive toughness, given the thickness of the adhesive layer is sufficiently small. Other adhesive bond studies examined the effect of the bond thickness on the bond toughness [12]. Thicker bonds had a toughness equal to that of the bulk adhesive while thinner bonds had a significantly reduced toughness. These results indicate that the examination of a crack constrained by rigid adherends can provide critical information relating to composite fracture toughness.

There has been little work in the area of theoretical predictions of composite fracture toughness based on constituent properties. Two models have been created to make such predictions, but they fall short of the goal because they rely on parameters that cannot be obtained [13, 14]. Crews *et al.* created a finite element model using discrete fibers and resin at the crack tip to examine the constraint that the fibers have on the resin, but they did not actually make toughness predictions [10]. The analysis was purely elastic and made simple estimates on plastic zones to investigate the likelihood that the fibers were inducing yielding in the resin and thereby increasing toughness.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Delamination experiments were conducted to examine the important mechanisms involved in composite fracture and to obtain a reliable measurement of delamination initiation. Furthermore, neat resin properties were measured as well so that they may be used as inputs to the FEM. The composite system IM7/977-3 was chosen as a preliminary material model to investigate. This material is quite prevalent in modern aerospace products and the 977-3 toughened epoxy was expected to exhibit behavior unlike that of brittle epoxies. The composite was initially in prepreg form and was cured in accordance with manufacturer recommended procedures, while the neat resin was provided as 3 mm thick cast plaques from the manufacturer, Cytac Engineered Materials.

The Mode I interlaminar delamination toughness of IM7/977-3 was measured in accordance with ASTM standard D5528 using the double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen. The specimens contained 28 unidirectional plies and a 13 μm thick Teflon insert at the midplane to create an initial delamination. Overall specimen dimensions were 150 x 25 x 7.1 mm. The unusually high thickness value is due to the high fiber areal weight of 290 g/m^2 . All specimens were dried for thirty hours to ensure a baseline “dry” condition during the test. Load was applied via hinges bonded to the ends of the specimens. Testing was performed on a servohydraulic testing machine and crack growth monitored using a traveling microscope.

Figure 2. IM7/977-3 Mode I Interlaminar Delamination Toughness.

Figure 2 shows the results of the DCB tests with the critical strain energy release rate, G_{IC} , being the measure for toughness. The horizontal axis lists the criteria for initiation: “NL” is the onset of nonlinearity in the load-displacement plot, “VIS” is the point at which the crack was visually seen to initially propagate, and “5%/MAX” is the point at which a line that has a slope equal to 5% less than

the initial linear region intersects the load-displacement plot, or the maximum value of the load-displacement plot, whichever comes first. The three values for each initiation criterion correspond to calculation methods: “MBT” is Modified Beam Theory, “CC” is Compliance Calibration, and “MCC” is Modified Compliance Calibration. The standard deviation on all values ranges from 6-8 J/m². It is evident that there is not a great deal of variation among the calculation methods or among the initiation criteria. However, audible cracking coincided with the onset of nonlinearity but was prior to visual examination of crack propagation. Thus, the nonlinear criterion may be the most accurate representation of initial crack propagation and is certainly the most conservative. This reasoning led to the choice of 175 J/m² as a representative value of the interlaminar delamination toughness. The manufacturer reports an interlaminar fracture toughness of 315 J/m² [15]. However, there is no information regarding how this information was obtained. This value is close to results obtained in these tests for *propagation* toughness. This may be representative of a common problem in the literature of not distinguishing between initiation and propagation toughness values. No other interlaminar toughness data for IM7/977-3 was found in the literature.

The toughness of the 977-3 neat resin was tested in accordance with ASTM standard D5045 for plastic materials. Compact tension (CT) specimens were machined from the 3 mm thick resin plaques. The specimens were approximately 15 mm on each side. Crack tips were created by tapping a razor blade into the machined notch. Tests were conducted using a servohydraulic testing machine and all specimens exhibited linear behavior up to the point of fracture, which was brittle in nature. While the fracture toughness, K_{IC} , can be measured entirely from a test on a CT specimen, the critical strain energy release rate, G_{IC} , can only be determined experimentally if an indentation test is performed as well. This consists of testing a CT specimen without a notch, thereby determining the compliance in the testing system. The energy used in deforming the testing system is subtracted from the measured energy required to cause fracture, resulting in the material’s true toughness. Of course, this measured G_{IC} can also be compared with a calculated G_{IC} that is computed by using K_{IC} and the material’s Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio. The average values for five specimens using these methods are listed in Table 1 with standard deviation in parentheses. The manufacturer reports a critical fracture toughness of 0.9 MPa•m^{1/2} and a critical strain energy release rate of 217 J/m² [15]. The values are listed as obtained from three-point bend tests, but there are no test details. Furthermore, no other toughness data for 977-3 was found in the literature. Although the difference in test methods may produce some discrepancies, it is unlikely that any mistakes made in these tests would lower the measured fracture toughness. Rather, inaccuracies such as a blunted crack tip or a non-plane-strain condition would artificially increase the fracture toughness. Thus, there is no clear explanation for the difference in measured values.

Table 1. 977-3 Neat Resin Mode I Fracture Properties.

K_{IC} (MPa m ^{0.5})	G_{IC} (J/m ²) from K_{IC}	G_{IC} (J/m ²) from data
0.82 (9.1%)	155.7 (17.9%)	156.6 (8.8%)

The compressive properties of the neat resin were also determined in order to obtain a measure of the material’s inelastic deformation behavior. Tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM standard D695 for rigid plastic materials. Right prism specimens measuring 3 mm x 6 mm x 12 mm were machined from the resin plaques and tested using the long axis in compression. The specimens were tested in a servohydraulic testing machine by inserting them in between compression discs with smooth polymer faces and placing Teflon in between the specimen ends and the disc faces to reduce friction. One disc mated into a ball and cup joint to minimize misalignment effects. The load-displacement plots were always nonlinear, however it is not clear whether the cause of the nonlinearity is geometric or inelastic deformation. The fact that the material showed no signs of permanent deformation and some specimens cracked at the end of the test indicates that the nonlinearity is most likely geometric in nature. Average results for five specimens are shown in Table 2 with standard deviation in parentheses; α and n are

Ramberg-Osgood parameters. It is important to note that if the nonlinearity in the load-displacement plot is geometric then the values listed are not representative of the material.

Table 2. 977-3 Neat Resin Compressive Properties.

Modulus (MPa)	0.2% Offset Yield Stress (MPa)	Max Stress (MPa)	α	n
2.86 (1.5%)	91.4 (2.6%)	131.7 (5.0%)	0.063 (4.8%)	4.64 (3.5 %)

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) conducted on the composite DCB specimens elucidated some of the important characteristics of the delamination initiation. Figure 3a clearly shows that there is a resin rich region that develops ahead of the crack tip. This is important because it indicates that delamination propagation occurs in a region that is composed primarily of resin. The crack tip resin rich region is analogous to that found in between plies and thus is representative of an actual delamination. However, the high fiber areal weight of this composite may have contributed to resin pockets that are larger than those found in most composites. The large regions of pure resin on the delamination surface in Figure 3b reinforce the theory that initial crack propagation occurs in areas composed predominantly of resin. Other microscopy indicated that there is good fiber/resin adhesion, demonstrating that toughness is not reduced by premature fiber/resin decohesion.

Figure 3. a) Crack tip in DCB specimen. b) DCB fracture surface.

ANALYTICAL INVESTIGATION

The review of the literature and the SEM of the IM7/977-3 specimens clearly indicate that plastic deformation and/or damage at the crack tip in the matrix of a composite is the primary energy dissipative mechanism in interlaminar fracture. Hence, an FEM was created that could specifically account for the inelastic deformation in the resin at the crack tip. This is best accomplished by discretely analyzing the resin and fibers at the crack tip in a manner similar to that used by Crews [10]. The fibers create the appropriate constraint on the resin, while the resin in the region at the crack tip and in the surrounding interfiber regions are allowed to plastically deform and contribute to the overall work of fracture. Rather than create a model that is entirely composed of discrete resin and fibers, a global homogeneous composite model drives a local model at the crack tip that contains the resin and fibers. The method for determining the delamination toughness is as follows. A global homogeneous composite DCB model determines the applied displacements for the local model. The applied displacements for the local model determine the deformation state at the crack tip and from this the J -integral is calculated. The global J -integral represents the strain energy release rate that would be determined experimentally. The local J -integral accounts for the inelastic deformation in the resin and

this value is compared with a resin critical fracture criterion. The global J -integral that results in the local value that meets the resin fracture criterion is the interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite.

The model was generated and run using the finite element software ABAQUS, version 6.2. The global model is a 2-D symmetric plane strain DCB that contains elastic homogeneous composite properties. The displacements for the local model are calculated and applied to the local model automatically by the ABAQUS *SUBMODEL command. The local model is also 2-D, plane strain, and symmetric and is one ply thick. It contains a resin rich layer at the crack tip beneath four layers of fibers alternating with three layers of resin. A homogeneous composite region surrounds these layers. Fibers are elastic and the resin is elastic-plastic; perfect bonding is assumed. A schematic of the local model is shown in Figure 4. The J -integral is evaluated in the global and local models using the ABAQUS *CONTOUR INTEGRAL command. This calculates the J -integral in successive contours around the crack tip until a final value is converged upon. Since the global model is elastic, the J -integral coincides with the closed form solution for the strain energy release rate in a DCB determined by Suo *et al.* [16], which includes a correction to the elementary beam theory for shear effects and a numerically determined correction factor.

The results of the composite and neat resin experiments, along with material properties available in the literature or from the manufacturer, were incorporated into the FEM. Some transverse fiber properties were estimated from composite properties. The elastic material properties used in the analysis are shown in Table 3. Lamina properties were calculated using standard micromechanics equations in order to maintain the AIM methodology of determining composite properties from constituents [3]. Calculated composite properties were close to those reported by the manufacturer [15]. The dimensions of the model including DCB size, ply thickness, and fiber spacing were determined from the experimental specimens, while fiber diameter was given by the manufacturer data.

Table 3. Material properties used in FEM.

Material	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{23}
IM7/977-3	168.0	9.55	4.35	3.42	0.26	0.40
IM7 Fibers	277.0	17.2	18.6	4.83	0.20	0.25
977-3 Resin	3.8	3.8	2.77	2.77	0.37	0.37

Figure 5. Local J -integrals for various resin rich thicknesses and resin behavior.

A parametric study was conducted to determine the sensitivity of the model to the resin rich region thickness and the incorporation of plasticity to the resin behavior. Figure 5 shows the results of the analyses in which a 200 N load was applied to the global model, resulting in a global J -integral of 332.0 J/m². Resin behavior was defined as elastic, perfectly plastic, or by deformation plasticity (*i.e.* Ramberg-Osgood behavior). Although the experimentally determined resin inelastic properties are questionable, varying the resin plastic behavior in the model serves to examine the model's applicability to materials with different plastic behavior. Note that the values listed for the resin rich region in the model are actually half the thickness of the resin rich

region in the actual composite. A 2 micron gap is a typical interfiber spacing while a 30 micron region exists immediately after the insert in Figure 3a. For this load a variation in thickness can change the J -integral by over 10% and it is clear that increasing the constraint on the crack tip (*i.e.* decreasing the thickness) increases the J -integral. This is expected because the crack tip stresses increase as the constraint is increased. Other studies in which the stiffness of the constraining layer was increased validated this behavior. As the stiffness increased the stresses increased and hence the J -integral increased. Plasticity has the effect of relieving the stresses at the crack tip and hence produces lower J -integral values. Perfect plasticity creates more yielded material than deformation plasticity and thus it has more of a stress relieving effect.

One can clearly see the effect that the constraint has on in the resin in Figure 6. All contour plots show equivalent plastic strain and depict the undeformed state. Figures 6a and 6c are of the local composite model and the Figures 6b and 6d are of a crack tip in a neat resin compact tension model. The dimensions are the same in all the pictures and the globally applied load is the same for the composite models, 200 N. The neat resin models have the same J -integral values as their corresponding composite models. The areas in grey are regions where the equivalent plastic strain is greater than 0.1. The grey areas in the resin rich region for both composite models are approximately the same – slightly over $8 \mu\text{m}^2$. However, the total yielded area in the model with the thinner region is $12 \mu\text{m}^2$ while it is $169 \mu\text{m}^2$ in the model with the thicker region. This is compared with $174 \mu\text{m}^2$ and $116 \mu\text{m}^2$ in the associated CT models. Furthermore, the magnitude of the highest plastic strains is much higher in the model with the thinner region. (The actual values of the strains are unrealistically high because of mesh refinement limitations at the crack tip - between 1 and 10 - but the comparison is instructive.) Two important conclusions can be drawn from these comparisons. The intensity of the strains is higher for a thinner resin rich region, but the total amount of yielded area is less. Furthermore, the intensity of the crack tip strains is much higher than the resin in the upper layers, indicating that the energy dissipation at the crack tip is most likely the

Figure 6. Equivalent plastic strain in local composite models with different resin rich region thicknesses and neat resin compact tension models at the same J -integral levels.

It is informative to compare the local J -integral that results from an applied global load and the associated global J -integral. Figure 7 compares these values over a wide range and for three different types of plastic behavior – the aforementioned perfect plasticity and deformation plasticity models in addition to Drucker-Prager behavior, in which the material exhibits pressure dependence in plasticity. The Drucker-Prager parameters used were $K=1$ and $\beta=\psi=20$ degrees, which are pressure sensitivity parameters. It is clear that the more plasticity that exists at the crack tip the lower the local J -integral will be. Furthermore, the difference between global and local values is more pronounced at higher load levels. It is important to note that this plot is comparing calculated J -integrals for a particular stress state, as opposed to critical fracture parameters. However, if the neat resin toughness was used as the fracture criterion at the local level then the plot would show the neat resin toughness versus composite toughness. This is obviously incorrect because it indicates that the more plastic behavior a neat resin exhibits the more likely it is to have a toughness less than that of the composite. Figure 1 with experimental data shows that this is not the case. Thus, another fracture criterion is needed.

DISCUSSION

As mentioned above, using a neat resin fracture criterion provides insight into the stress state that leads to fracture, they do not indicate when the resin will fracture. As mentioned above, using a neat resin fracture

toughness is inadequate. It is useful to examine the results of adhesive bond toughness experiments that vary the thickness of the bond [12]. Work of this sort depicts the behavior shown in Figure 8 where the brittle resins exhibit no thickness effect while the ductile resins show a marked thickness effect. The explanation for this behavior is usually that the thicker bonds have the toughness of the bulk adhesive, but there is an increase in toughness with decreasing thickness as the constraint causes an increase in the amount of material that is plastically deforming. Eventually decreasing thicknesses have the effect of decreasing the amount of material that is plastically deforming, thereby decreasing the toughness. This results in a substantial loss in toughness for the bond when compared to the bulk adhesive. Although the thickness of the bonds in this plot are not on the scale of the resin rich region in a composite, Chai has tested such bonds and discovered that the toughness of the bond was almost identical to that of the composite with the same resin [7].

The adhesive bond thickness studies have implications for the current work because they indicate that the constraint on the resin causes a change to occur in its critical fracture level that cannot be simply explained by comparing global and local J -integrals. The model developed in this research may still be used as a tool to determine the extent of plastic deformation at the crack tip, which is the largest contributing factor to the work of fracture, and it may also be used to determine the intensity of crack tip strains. The latter of these phenomena may explain why fracture occurs in a constrained layer with reduced plastic area. The local J -integral, however, must be compared with a fracture criterion that accounts for the change in constraint on the material and the decrease in volume that is available to deform plastically. At the moment, this fracture criterion must be determined experimentally.

Figure 8. Adhesive bond toughness vs. bond thickness for an epoxy (squares) and a rubber-toughened epoxy (circles) [12].

For a brittle material with a low critical strain energy release rate, the model indicates that there is little difference between the local and global J -integrals. The plastic zone size of the neat resin may be small enough that the composite actually enlarges the volume of plastically deforming material, which would increase the toughness of the constrained resin. The model describes this behavior in the difference between the global and local J -integral. The increase in available fracture area from the corrugated roof shape of the fracture surface may also explain the increase in toughness for a brittle resin. Furthermore, if composite interlaminar toughness values are artificially high as reported due to the measurement of propagation values, then the composite toughnesses may be closer to the neat resin values than previously considered. In the case of the experimental system considered here, the neat resin was found to be more brittle than expected and the toughness was quite close to that of the composite.

If a relationship between the volume of plastically deformed material and fracture levels in constrained ductile resins can be determined, then the model will be of great use in determining fracture toughness. However, unless the fracture criterion is known *a priori*, a prediction of toughness cannot be made from constituent data alone. Data from adhesive bond tests using neat resins with thin layers on the order of the interply resin thickness could be used as an estimate of composite toughness while the model could be used to explain the differences between the neat resin and composite toughnesses. This combined process of neat resin experiments, in the form of adhesive bond tests, and analysis would certainly be beneficial in the evaluation of candidate resin systems. The composite fracture values could be used in design studies before the actual composite is fabricated.

CONCLUSIONS

A finite element model has been created to examine the difference between the global and local behavior in a composite fracture specimen with the goal of predicting composite interlaminar delamination toughness from constituent properties. The model indicates that an increase in the constraint on the crack tip increases the stress state at the crack tip and hence the J -integral as well. Furthermore, plasticity relieves stresses at the crack tip and therefore reduces the local J -integral and increases the difference between the global and local J -integral. The most important conclusion of the model is that intensity of the strains in a plastically deforming crack tip are higher in a more highly

constrained crack tip, but the total plastic area is less. This may serve as the chief explanation as to why the toughness of a composite is less than its more ductile resin. The neat resin toughness is inadequate as a fracture criterion, but a constrained toughness value at an appropriate thickness level is more appropriate. Neat resin adhesive bond tests could be used as an estimate of composite toughness and the model could be used to elucidate the mechanisms that change the resin toughness in the composite.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This effort was jointly accomplished by the Boeing led team and the United States Government under the guidance of NAST. This work was funded by DARPA/DSO and administered by NAST under Technology Investment Agreement N00421-01-3-0098. The program would like to acknowledge the guidance and support of Dr. Steve Wax and Dr. Leo Christodoulou of DARPA/DSO for this effort. The technical monitor for the program is Dr. Ray Meilunas of NAVAIR.

REFERENCES

1. Hahn, G.H., K.M. Nelson, and C.R. Saff. *Accelerated Insertion of Materials-Composites*. in *34th International SAMPE Conference*. 2002.
2. Chamis, C.C., *Simplified Composite Micromechanics Equations for Hygral, Thermal, and Mechanical-Properties*. SAMPE Quarterly-Society for the Advancement of Material and Process Engineering, 1984. **15**(3): p. 14-23.
3. Hashin, Z.H., *Analysis of properties of fiber composites with anisotropic constituents*. Journal of Applied Mechanics, 1979. **46**: p. 543-550.
4. Hunston, D.L., et al., *Matrix resin effects in composite delamination: Mode I fracture aspects*, in *Toughened composites*, N.J. Johnston, Editor. 1987, American Society for Testing and Materials: Philadelphia. p. 74-94.
5. Bradley, W.L., *Relationship of matrix toughness to interlaminar fracture toughness*, in *Application of Fracture Mechanics to Composite Materials*, K. Friedrich, Editor. 1989, Elsevier Science: 159-187.
6. Bradley, W.L. and R.N. Cohen, *Matrix deformation and fracture in graphite-reinforced epoxies*, in *Delamination and debonding of materials*, W.S. Johnson, Editor. 1985, American Society for Testing and Materials: Philadelphia. p. 389-410.
7. Chai, H., *On the Correlation between the Mode-I Failure of Adhesive Joints and Laminated Composites*. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 1986. **24**(3): p. 413-&.
8. Chai, H., *The Characterization of Mode-I Delamination Failure in Non-Woven, Multidirectional Laminates*. Composites, 1984. **15**(4): p. 277-290.
9. Lee, S.M., *A Comparison of Fracture-Toughness of Matrix Controlled Failure Modes - Delamination and Transverse Cracking*. Journal of Composite Materials, 1986. **20**(2): p. 185-196.
10. Crews Jr., J.H., K.N. Shivakumar, and I.S. Raju, *A fiber-resin micromechanics analysis of the delamination front in a DCB specimen*. 1988, NASA-TM-100540.
11. Wang, S.S., J.F. Mandell, and F.J. McGarry, *Analysis of Crack Tip Stress-Field in DCB Adhesive Fracture Specimens*. International Journal of Fracture, 1978. **14**(1): p. 39-58.
12. Hunston, D.L., A.J. Kinloch, and S.S. Wang, *Micromechanics of Fracture in Structural Adhesive Bonds*. Journal of Adhesion, 1989. **28**(2-3): p. 103-114.
13. Ivens, J., et al., *Interlaminar Fracture-Toughness of CFRP Influenced by Fiber Surface-Treatment .2. Modeling of the Interface Effect*. Composites Science and Technology, 1995. **54**(2): p. 147-159.
14. Lee, S.M., *Correlation between Resin Material Variables and Transverse Cracking in Composites*. Journal of Materials Science, 1984. **19**(7): p. 2278-2288.
15. Fiberite, *Material Data Sheet*. 1995.
16. Suo, Z., et al., *Orthotropy Rescaling and Implications for Fracture in Composites*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 1991. **28**(2): p. 235-248.